

Review Paper

Cost-Benefit analysis of urban nature-based solutions: A systematic review of approaches and scales with a focus on benefit valuation

Alessia Chelli^{a,d}, Luke Brander^{b,c}, Davide Geneletti^{d,*}

^a Department of Economics and Management, University of Trento, via Inama 5, 38122 Trento, Italy

^b Institute for Environmental Studies, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam, the Netherlands

^c Institute of Earth System Sciences, Leibniz University Hannover, Hannover, Germany

^d Department Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering, University of Trento, via Mesiano 77, 38123 Trento, Italy

ABSTRACT

Urban nature-based solutions (NBS) are increasingly recognized as an effective strategy to address urban sustainability challenges. Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) is a widely used method for assessing the economic feasibility of NBS interventions and supporting decision-makers in comparing different investment alternatives. Performing a CBA, however, is complex and requires making methodological choices and assumptions, such as choosing the discount rate and the temporal horizon, which can significantly affect the outcome estimates. Moreover, the inclusion of the full range of costs and benefits can be challenging due to difficulties and uncertainties in estimating their monetary value and accounting for their spatial and temporal dynamics. The objective of this research is to critically analyze current applications of CBA on urban NBS in the scientific literature, identifying trends, limitations, and research gaps. To achieve this, we conducted a systematic review of articles published between 2000 and 2022, resulting in 114 observations of CBAs for urban NBS. The review compared CBA approaches and scales, focusing on the monetary valuation of costs and benefits, as well as the spatial and temporal dynamics of benefits. Our results indicate a predominance of CBAs with a social, as opposed to private, perspective, and with a focus on building solutions and small-scale NBS interventions. Moreover, we found a general lack of consideration for environmental externalities among the costs, and an incomplete inclusion of the full range of benefits, often due to difficulties in estimating their monetary values. We also found that CBA studies usually do not consider the variability in NBS performance over time. Finally, most studies reported a positive CBA outcome, suggesting that NBS are generally economically advantageous.

1. Introduction

Nature-based solutions (NBS) are based on the use of nature to address societal challenges through the provision of ecosystem services (ES), as well as environmental, social and economic co-benefits. NBS in an urban context can range from large-scale interventions, such as urban parks and forests, to smaller initiatives such as rain gardens, bioswales, green roofs, and living walls. These interventions can offer a wide range of benefits, and can be strategically combined to address specific issues (Almeida et al., 2021; Melo et al., 2020; Raymond et al., 2017). For instance, larger NBS projects can enhance the social well-being of city residents, and at the same time contribute to mitigating heatwaves, managing stormwater runoff, and improving air quality (Aevermann & Schmude, 2015; Escobedo et al., 2011; Livesley et al., 2016). Even smaller-scale interventions can have a significant impact. For example, a single green roof can improve the energy efficiency of the building it is implemented on, and provide benefits to the community such as enhancing biodiversity and improving the aesthetics of the urban environment (Haghighatafshar et al., 2018; Zinzi & Agnoli, 2012).

Nevertheless, NBS can also produce negative impacts. These can arise from activities such as irrigation, pruning, and replanting, which gradually exert stress on the environment, leading to both financial costs and environmental impacts (Babí Almenar et al., 2023). Studies evaluating urban NBS often overlook these adverse effects (Keeler et al., 2019; Larrey-Lassalle et al., 2022).

The planning of NBS interventions can be supported by economic analysis to assess the societal return on investment, as well as to make comparisons between alternative investment options (Le Coent et al., 2021; Wild et al., 2017). A number of methods can be used in NBS appraisal, including Life-Cycle Costing (LCC), Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA), Multicriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA), and Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) (Adem Esmail & Geneletti, 2018; Brander et al., 2018; Geneletti & Ferretti, 2015; Le Coent et al., 2021; Swarr et al., 2011). LCC accounts for financial costs and externalities, converting them into monetary flows over the NBS life cycle (Swarr et al., 2011). CEA measures the ratio between the discounted costs incurred over the NBS's lifetime – expressed in monetary units – and a specified NBS output, usually expressed in physical units (e.g., tons of CO₂ sequestered, or m³

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: alessia.chelli@unitn.it (A. Chelli), lukebrander@gmail.com (L. Brander), davide.geneletti@unitn.it (D. Geneletti).

of water retained). It is typically used in decision-making contexts that have a defined policy objective, as it enables the identification of the lowest cost option to achieve a specific environmental or social outcome (Brander et al., 2018; Le Coent et al., 2021). MCDA is a systematic approach that compares the advantages and disadvantages of alternative interventions. Alternatives are evaluated using a defined set of qualitative and quantitative criteria, that are weighted based on stakeholders' preferences and policy goals (Adem Esmail & Geneletti, 2018; Geneletti & Ferretti, 2015). Finally, CBA quantifies the extent to which benefits from a project exceed its costs over a specified period of time.

In CBA, benefits and costs are expressed in monetary terms, and future values are discounted to enable their aggregation and comparison (Boardman et al., 2018). In the evaluation of environmental projects CBA incorporates not only the financial costs and benefits, but also the environmental and social externalities that affect the community (Castañer et al., 2020; Neumann & Hack, 2022). CBA allows decision-makers to make informed decisions when evaluating investment alternatives, whether between alternative types of NBS or between NBS and conventional "gray" infrastructure (Johnson et al., 2020; Le Coent et al., 2021). Table 1 provides an overview of the main indicators of project performance that can be estimated through CBA (Arrow et al., 1997; Hanley & Spash, 1993).

Various types of CBA exist, and within the context of environmental projects, including NBS, it is important to distinguish between private CBA and social CBA (Brander et al., 2018; European Commission, 2015a; OECD, 2018). Private CBA assesses the economic viability of a project from the perspective of the investor, considering only the costs and benefits that they directly incur. This approach is particularly useful to evaluate an NBS investment on private properties, such as installing a green roof on a residential building, as it allows to estimate the direct profitability of the measure for the private investor. Social CBA also includes the costs and benefits that affect the society and is usually applied for public policies and investments to evaluate their overall impact on the community (Teotónio et al., 2021). It plays a crucial role in the economic evaluation of NBS, as it not only provides a measure of the financial feasibility of the investment but also considers the broader environmental and economic impact on society. In this context, it is important to identify the groups in society that potentially benefit from or incur costs related to the NBS, which in some cases, might extend beyond the population living in the immediate vicinity of the project area. These costs and benefits represent the monetary value of the negative and positive externalities derived from the project. Examples of

negative externalities are pollution emissions, or ecosystem losses, while examples of positive externalities include enhanced provision of ES, such as increase in recreational opportunities, health improvements, CO₂ sequestration, or increases in biodiversity (Molinos-Senante et al., 2010; OECD, 2018).

Performing a CBA requires addressing critical issues that can impact the final outcome, such as selecting the discount rate and the temporal horizon of the analysis. The selection of the discount rate for an investment evaluation is an uncertain and exogenously determined parameter that represents the opportunity costs of investments with a long-term horizon. Setting a discount rate that is too high can hinder the implementation of the project, while setting it too low could result in inefficient investments. The debate regarding the most appropriate discount rate to be used, particularly in the economics of climate change, remains ongoing (Aerts et al., 2014; Hein et al., 2016; OECD, 2018; Drupp et al., 2018). The temporal horizon refers to the timeframe during which costs and benefits are assessed. The question arises as to how far into the future these effects should be estimated, since considering shorter periods may lead to the exclusion of some impacts (OECD, 2018; Zhuang et al., 2007). Usually, the standard practice is to set the time horizon as the duration of the investment's physical or economic life. For social CBA the issue is more challenging, since it is hard to predict how long the social and environmental impacts of the project will last (OECD, 2018).

In CBA, all costs and benefits arising from the project need to be expressed in monetary terms. This gives rise to a significant challenge when performing social CBA on NBS projects, considering that it is not always feasible to estimate the monetary value of the environmental and social impacts (Neumann & Hack, 2022; OECD, 2018). This can result in incomplete or partial analysis, undermining for example the comparison between NBS and "gray" solutions or the development of appropriate investment plans for a given NBS (Sandin et al., 2022; Swann et al., 2021). Regarding costs, private CBA usually considers both initial investment expenses and operation and maintenance costs that arise over time. These costs are usually well defined and directly expressed in monetary terms. Social CBA requires the consideration of negative environmental and social impacts, which might occur off-site and over an extended period of time (Babí Almenar et al., 2023). These costs are usually not well defined and estimating their value can be complex. In the context of NBS, this could refer, for example, to the emission of GHGs resulting from its implementation. Several authors have recently pointed out the lack of consideration of negative environmental externalities in the economic valuation of NBS (Babí Almenar et al., 2023; Keeler et al., 2019). Private CBA includes the direct benefits that the investor gains from NBS. For example, green roofs provide energy savings for heating and cooling, and increase the property value of the building. Social CBA extends the private CBA framework to include the positive environmental and social externalities from NBS, which typically take the form of increased provision of ES. Including ES in social CBA often requires the application of non-market valuation techniques. This is because many ES are not traded in markets, and therefore do not have readily observable prices (Brander et al., 2018; Molinos-Senante et al., 2010). Non-market valuation methods involve the combination of biophysical data and methods to quantify the supply ES, and economic methods to estimate the value of these flows in monetary terms. They can also be used in combination with socio-cultural methods to gain a broader understanding of the importance of ES to society (Brander et al., 2018).

The impacts of NBS can vary over space and time and these variations need to be identified and measured in both private and social CBAs (Babí Almenar et al., 2023; Hansjurgens, 2004). The spatial distribution of NBS benefits can vary depending on the type of NBS, its characteristics and size (Cortinovis & Geneletti, 2019). Moreover, NBS impacts can be observed at different spatial scales, with some ES potentially extending beyond the area where the NBS is implemented. For example, the cooling effect of NBS can reduce the energy consumption of

Table 1
Cost-benefit analysis main indicators of investment performance.

CBA indicators		
Net Present Value (NPV)	Sum of all future benefit flows over the investment's lifetime net of costs, discounted to the present value. A positive NPV indicates that the investment is economically viable.	$NVP = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{B_t - C_t}{(1+r)^t}$ B_t benefits, C_t costs, t time, r discount rate
Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR)	The ratio of the sum of discounted benefits and the sum of discounted costs. A BCR greater than 1 indicates that the investment is economically viable.	$BCR = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^T \frac{B_t}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^T \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t}}$ B_t benefits, C_t costs, t time, r discount rate
Payback Period (PBP)	The length of time it takes for the benefits of the investment to equal the initial costs	$PBP = \frac{\text{Investment cost}}{\text{annual cash inflow}}$
Internal Rate of Return (IRR)	The discount rate at which a project's NPV becomes zero. If the IRR exceeds the rate of return on alternative investments with similar risk, the project can be considered economically viable.	$0 = NVP = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{B_t - C_t}{(1+r)^t}$ B_t benefits, C_t costs, t time, r discount rate

buildings. The benefit of this effect can be accounted both at the building level, as a reduction in energy costs, and at the global level, as a decrease in CO₂ emissions and consequently climate change. Therefore, assessing the value of NBS at different spatial scales involves understanding at what scale and for whom the benefits are obtained (Brander et al., 2018; Martín-López et al., 2009). Concerning the temporal distribution of NBS effects, the “biological time” of NBS (i.e., the time required for biological processes, such as plant growth, to occur) plays a crucial role in determining when the NBS becomes fully functional (Nature4Cities, 2018). Some ES are immediately provided upon the installation of the NBS, while others require years before becoming fully effective (Babí Almenar et al., 2023; Giordano et al., 2020; Kabisch et al., 2016; Rau et al., 2018; C. Raymond et al., 2017). For example, building an urban park can increase recreational opportunities and improve air quality in a specific area. However, the increase in recreational use is immediate, while the effect on air quality may take years, due to the time required for plants to grow. Moreover, alteration in biophysical attributes that occur over a period of time (e.g., changes in the height of trees, crown width, or leaf area) or the impact of exogenous factors (e.g., climatic conditions, or management actions) can enhance or reduce the potential of NBS to deliver specific ES (Babí Almenar et al., 2023). When conducting economic assessments of NBS, it is essential to account for these temporal variations. The quantification of temporal changes in ES flows and values as a function of ecosystem dynamics, however, is not straightforward (Hein et al., 2016). As noted by Rau et al. (2018), the attention on temporal dynamics in the empirical literature on ES is limited, accounting for only 3 % of existing work (Rau et al., 2018). Since estimating the spatial and temporal changes of ES can be complex, these dynamics are often overlooked in ES assessments and, as a result, are not considered in the economic evaluation of NBS (Di Pirro et al., 2023; Elliot et al., 2019). To overcome this issue, it is important to combine biophysical analysis with monetary assessment of NBS, and to consider both biophysical and monetary values in the decision-making process (Babí Almenar et al., 2023).

Due to the challenges discussed above, CBA estimates can be highly uncertain (Asplund & Eliasson, 2016). One way to measure this uncertainty is to perform sensitivity analysis. Although it does not resolve the inherent issues within CBA, it allows to measure the degree to which the CBA result depends on specific parameters and reveals the potential variability and robustness of the economic assessment (Locatelli et al., 2020; Wilbers, 2022). The European Commission recommends considering variables as critical for which a $\pm 1\%$ variation in value results in a change of more than 1 % of the NPV (European Commission, 2015a).

Given these considerations, the objective of this research is to examine how CBA of urban NBS has been conducted in the literature, with specific reference to the critical issues and challenges previously identified, and provide recommendations for future research and applications. To this purpose, our review framework focuses on:

- i) CBA methods (type of CBA and main elements, such as discount rate, temporal horizon, types of benefits and costs included, uncertainty analyses) and outcomes;
- ii) Application context: type of NBS and spatial scale, decision-making problem addressed;
- iii) Valuation of benefits and costs: approaches adopted and spatial and temporal distribution of the benefits.

2. Methods

2.1. Article selection

The literature search was conducted using Elsevier’s Scopus© and Web of Science© bibliographic databases. The search was run by combining two broad criteria: i) the reference to NBS; ii) the reference to CBA. To ensure maximum inclusivity, we incorporated the term “green infrastructure”, often used interchangeably with NBS, along with a list of

NBS typologies. The final search string is the result of several attempts to capture the widest possible sample of publications. The search was carried out on the 30th of November 2022 using the combination of keywords shown in Table 2, and was limited to English-language publications from 2000 to 2022. A total of 849 records were identified.

2.2. Article screening

Fig. 1 presents a flow diagram of the article identification and screening process. From the initial sample of 849 studies, we first removed all the duplicate records, as well as book chapters and conference papers, in order to focus on peer-reviewed publications. Subsequently, the selected articles were screened based on title, abstract, and keywords. Studies were included for full-text review if: (1) they refer to case studies conducted in urban and peri-urban areas; and (2) they address at least one type of urban NBS; and (3) they include a CBA. The full-text reading process led to the exclusion of an additional 77 papers, where CBA was only mentioned or superficially described (i.e., they did not provide sufficient detail required for our analysis). We ultimately obtained a final sample of 48 publications.

2.3. Review framework

Fig. 2 represents the review framework developed to include the main stages of CBA, with a specific focus on NBS costs and benefits evaluation. Some of the analyses were conducted at the study level, while others occurred at the NBS observation, and NBS group levels. In defining NBS observations, we applied the following criteria:

- When an article examined multiple NBS and included a CBA for each of them, we considered each NBS as a separate observation;
- If an article conducted a multi-level CBA for the same NBS (such as both private and social CBA), we only considered the most comprehensive analysis as an NBS observation;
- If a study investigated the same NBS across multiple spatial scales while maintaining constant CBA elements (e.g., identical benefits, costs, time scales, and evaluation methodologies), we included only the primary analysis.

The review also includes studies that have assessed both NBS and technical solutions. In this case only NBS were included in the review. NBS types were categorized, whenever possible, according to the classification from Castellar et al. (2021) and grouped into the broader categories identified by the World Bank (2021). We added the category

Table 2
Keyword combination for literature search.

TITLE-ABS-KEY	AND	TITLE-ABS-KEY
“nature-based solution” OR “nature-based solutions” OR “nature-based” OR “green infrastructure” OR “green-blue infrastructure” OR “swale” OR “urban park” OR “green space” OR “green area” OR “urban trees” OR “street trees” OR “green wall” OR “green roof” OR “green facade” OR “vertical garden” OR “urban garden” OR “community garden” OR “urban agriculture” OR “greenway” OR “vertical greening system” OR “green corridor” OR “green route” OR “urban forest” OR “rain garden” OR “natural swale” OR “bioswale” OR “urban wetland” OR “constructed wetland” OR “retention pond” OR “detention pond” OR “permeable pavement”		“benefit-cost analysis” OR “cost-benefit analysis” OR “benefit cost analysis” OR “cost benefit analysis”

Fig. 1. Flow diagram illustrating the stages of the literature review.

“combination of solutions” to describe cases in which the analysis was conducted jointly for a combination of different NBS types, without disaggregating individual NBS.

In the first part of the review, we provide a general overview of the studies by describing the type of CBA performed, the type of NBS, the geographical location of the intervention, the decision-making problems addressed, and the spatial scales of NBS implementation.

In particular, the decision-making problems addressed by the CBA were classified into the following categories:

- Evaluation of an individual NBS: assessing the economic feasibility of a single NBS;
- Evaluation of a combination of solutions: assessing the economic feasibility of a single combination of solutions (i.e., joint implementation of different types of NBS or a mix of NBS and technical solutions);
- Comparison of alternative NBS: comparing the economic feasibility of alternative NBS interventions (i.e., different types of NBS or the same type of NBS applied at different locations or scales);
- Comparison of NBS and technical solutions: comparing the economic feasibility of NBS interventions with technical solutions;
- Comparison of different combinations of solutions: comparing the economic feasibility of various combinations of solutions (i.e., multiple types of NBS or a mix of NBS and technical solutions).

We categorized the spatial scale of NBS implementation into the following groups:

- Site level: a single building or plot of land;
- Neighborhood level: small area within a city (e.g., a street or an area around a site of interest);
- District level: a portion of a city;
- City level: the entire city;
- Metropolitan level: a larger region that encompasses multiple cities or municipalities.

In cases where the spatial scale was not explicitly mentioned in the study, we classified it based on the size of the intervention or the area of implementation.

In the second part of the review we identified and compared the main

CBA components and outcomes. Specifically, we looked at: the discount rate and time horizon used, the type of costs and benefits included, the CBA outcome, and whether the study addressed CBA uncertainty. Tables A2.a and A2.b in the Supplementary Material provide a description of the cost and benefit categories used. To avoid double counting, we included only those benefits for which a monetary value was estimated, thereby avoiding the inclusion of secondary benefits that arose from other benefits. The outcomes were classified into three categories, based on the results in terms of Net Present Value (NPV) or Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR). A “mixed” category was used to record studies with outcomes that were both positive and negative. This occurred when different benefit and cost estimations were performed (e.g., conservative and optimistic value estimations), resulting in both positive and negative NPV.

The third part of the review focused on the analysis of the methods used to evaluate NBS benefits and costs. Specifically, we reviewed the sources of cost estimates according to the following categories:

- Academic literature: estimates based on values reported in other scientific studies;
- Expert consultation: estimates based on local data consultation or interviews with experts and companies;
- Price lists: estimates based on the consultation of price lists and technical reports;
- Carbon price: estimates through carbon taxes or CO₂ equivalent values;
- Real cost value: actual monetary costs of implemented NBS, derived from ex-post CBA.

For benefits, we reviewed and compared the monetary valuation approaches, the relationship between the spatial scale of the NBS implementation and the distribution of the economic benefit derived from it, and their temporal distribution. To classify the monetary valuation approaches, we followed the classification identified by Brander et al. (2018), with the addition of the “avoided cost” category. To account for the spatial extent of the benefits, we examined how the different benefits were distributed in space. Essentially, we analysed the areas where the economic value of each benefit is realized and identified the distribution of people or groups who were benefiting. In this analysis, we employed the same categories used for the spatial scale of implementation, and added the “global” category, which includes benefits with a global impact.

Specifically, we recorded information on:

- Dominant spatial scale of NBS implementation: the spatial scale of NBS implementation at which each benefit has been predominantly included in the CBA;
- Dominant spatial scale of benefits value estimates: spatial scale at which the benefits have been estimated;
- Proportion of benefits evaluated at the same spatial scale as NBS implementation

Finally, for each category of NBS, we investigated the time frame over which the related benefits have been included in the CBA. Specifically, we analyzed whether studies accounted for benefits starting from the year of NBS implementation, considered them to be delayed, or extended their impact beyond the operational lifespan of the NBS. In cases where the study did not specify benefit time frames, we assumed their inclusion for every year throughout the analysis.

3. Results

3.1. General overview of the studies

Our review identified 114 NBS observations, across different types of NBS (Fig. 3). While building solutions have been extensively studied (68

Fig. 2. Review framework of the selected literature.

cases), the other types of NBS received less attention, with only a few observations identified.

The reviewed case studies were carried out in 23 countries. Most took place in Europe (23 studies), followed by Asia (11 studies), the United States (8 studies), and Latin America (5 studies). Only one study was conducted in Africa.

Most of the observations applied a social CBA, as illustrated in Fig. 4. Only 7 observations included exclusively private CBA. In these studies, private CBA was used to evaluate the profitability of installing NBS from the building owner's (Perini & Rosasco, 2016; Rosasco & Perini, 2018) or local authority's perspectives (Shazmin & Zulkifli, 2020), as well as to assess the use of economic incentives to encourage NBS adoption by private owners (Godyn, 2022). In many instances, building solutions were assessed using both private and social CBA. In particular, some of these assessments used multi-level CBA, which separately analyzed the financial (i.e., direct costs and benefits from the owner's perspective), economic (i.e., the added value to the local economy), and socio-environmental impacts (i.e., contribution to the environment and society) (Almeida et al., 2021; Matos Silva et al., 2019; Melo et al., 2020; Teotónio et al., 2018). These analyses frequently demonstrated that NBS

projects, while financially unattractive, became viable when social and environmental benefits were considered.

In the reviewed literature, CBA was performed either for ex-ante or ex-post economic evaluation of a single solution (15 studies), and more frequently, to compare different investment alternatives (33 studies). In the former case, CBA was conducted either on one type of NBS (13 studies) or on a combination of solutions (2 studies). When comparing different investment alternatives, CBA was primarily used to identify the most cost-effective solution to achieve specific urban goals, such as flood adaptation (Du et al., 2020; Velasco et al., 2018), or mitigation of the urban heat island effect (Johnson et al., 2020), or to compare the economic feasibility of different alternatives to be implemented in a specific location (Benis et al., 2018). In these cases, CBA has been performed to compare the outcome of both individual measures (28 studies) or a combination of solutions (5 studies). When comparing individual measures, 13 studies focused exclusively on NBS (i.e., comparing different types of NBS, or the same type of NBS in different size or location), while 15 studies compared NBS with technical solutions. These studies estimated the CBA outcomes of the individual measures, with a few also reporting outcomes of combined alternatives.

Fig. 3. Distribution of the NBS types analyzed in the reviewed studies.

Fig. 4. Distribution of the type of CBA among NBS categories.

Fig. 5. Distribution of the spatial scale of implementation among NBS categories.

Fig. 5 illustrates the spatial scales at which NBS were implemented. The site scale represents the most common category, mainly involving interventions targeting specific buildings or plots. In terms of NBS categories, building solutions mainly consist of site-specific interventions (41 cases). These studies evaluate the economic viability of NBS in distinct settings, such as underground passages (Melo et al., 2020), railway stations (Matos Silva et al., 2019), educational buildings (Wu & Smith, 2011; Yao et al., 2018), and private commercial structures such as office and industrial complexes (Berto et al., 2018; Rosasco & Perini, 2018). A subset of research conducted CBA on building solutions implemented at broader spatial scales, for example as part of a combination of measures to reach a specific adaptation goal (Johnson et al., 2020; Locatelli et al., 2020). None of the reviewed studies conducted a CBA for bioretention NBS implemented at the site level. This NBS category has been mainly studied at the neighborhood (13 cases) and district scales (9 cases), while a limited number of studies expanded their scope to encompass city-wide (3 cases) and metropolitan applications (3 cases). In these cases, the economic performance of the NBS was evaluated alongside other solutions, as part of combined adaptation strategies, primarily related to urban flood adaptation or stormwater management, or implemented across multiple areas. CBA of urban forests include comprehensive evaluations of street trees or urban parks within specific neighborhoods (4 cases) or entire cities (3 cases), with only one case at the site level, assessing the value of an urban forest on an University campus in Ghana (Dumenu, 2013). Urban farming studies have only conducted CBA on individual community gardens at the site level (4 cases). Open green spaces, on the other hand, have only been studied at the city scale (3 cases). Lastly, constructed wetlands have been examined at site (1 case), neighborhood (1 case), and city (1 case) scales.

3.2. Main components and outputs of CBA

The review showed that a range of different discount rates has been used in the case studies. Most of the CBAs applied a uniform discount rate to estimate the present value of costs and benefits (90 cases). Fig. 6 shows the distribution of the discount rates applied in these cases. A smaller subset of studies diverged from this approach. In particular, some studies used different discount rate to estimated multiple NPVs for the same NBS observation (5 cases). Others used different discount rates when conducting social and private CBAs (2 cases), while others used declining discount rates (DDR) (2 cases). Some interesting applications are the study from Johnson et al. (2021) and Berto et al. (2018). The former used different discount rates for private and social CBA, applying 3 % and 2.1 % rates to private and social costs and benefits respectively. The latter study used a declining rate, applying a 3.5 % discount rate for the first 30 years of the social CBA, and a 3 % discount rate for the subsequent 35 years. Finally, for 12 NBS cases, the discount rate was not specified.

The selection of the discount rate is significantly influenced by the socio-economic context of the country where the CBA is conducted. Our findings indicate that, in Europe, the discount rates applied to NBS range from 3 % to 8.5 %, in Asia from 4 % to 12 %, and in Latin America from

4 % to 6 %, while North American rates are slightly lower, varying between 2.8 % and 5 %. The single African case used a discount rate of 3.5 %.

Fig. 7 illustrates the temporal horizons applied in CBA of NBS. Six observations have been excluded from the analysis because the studies did not mention the temporal horizon used. In general, the temporal horizon reflects the expected lifetime of the infrastructure. The results indicate some variability within each NBS category, but overall suggests a preference for long-term horizons. An exception was noted in one study related to the assessment of average annual net benefits for street trees in Modesto, CA, which focused on a single year (McPherson, 2003).

Table 3 shows the distribution of the categories of benefits included in the CBA for each typology of NBS. Table A4 of the Supplementary Material provides more detailed information about the benefits considered at each spatial level of NBS implementation. In general, the types of benefits included in the CBA vary with the type of NBS. Most of the CBAs of building solutions include benefits that provide a direct advantage to the building itself. These include aesthetic appreciation, increased infrastructure longevity due to the protective capacity of the NBS, which delays the need for replacing building components (e.g., roofs), and energy savings resulting from the reduced demand for cooling and heating through improved thermal insulation. Many studies also accounted for environmental benefits, such as improved air quality, derived from both the CO₂ and air pollutant sequestration by plants, and the reduction in pollutant emissions as a result of increased thermal efficiency. Regulation of water flows and flood risk reduction are also considered in several studies, particularly in relation to green roofs. The main benefits included in the CBAs of bioretention NBS are those related to water management, such as the reduction of flood risk, regulation of water flows, and water treatment. This is expected, as this category of NBS is specifically designed to manage water and mitigate water-related extreme events. Other types of benefits have been considered in a limited number of observations. These include aesthetic appreciation, air quality improvement, and subsidies and tax reduction (i.e. reduction in water management fees). CBAs of urban forests mainly include benefits related to air quality improvement, water management, and enhanced mental and physical health. The remaining categories of NBS encompass a limited number of observations, and it is therefore not possible to overly generalize the results.

Table 4 presents the distribution of CBA cost categories. Nearly all cases included investment (i.e., initial financial outlays required to design, plan, and implement NBS) and operation and maintenance costs (i.e., expenses necessary to keep the NBS in good condition and ensure its proper functioning). In some cases, environmental costs were also included. These costs constitute the negative environmental externalities of the NBS, such as pollution generated during the production phases of green roofs (Melo et al., 2020), and rooftop farming (Benis et al., 2018) or CO₂ emissions from excavation activities to build a constructed wetland (García-Herrero et al., 2022). Opportunity costs were considered only in few observations. This cost represents the foregone benefits when one option is selected over another viable alternative, and therefore, its application is contingent upon the type of NBS under consideration. Residual costs have been included in a few

Fig. 6. Discount rate distribution among NBS categories.

Fig. 7. Temporal horizon distribution among NBS categories.

cases, and represent the residual potential use value of the NBS, as their services will be provided beyond the end of the CBA evaluation period (Locatelli et al., 2020). Removal and replacement costs have been mainly considered in cases involving building solutions. Lastly, the “Other” category encompasses residual types of costs such as administration, co-creation costs and security-related expenses, for example the inspection costs incurred to evaluate a roof’s structural capacity in the case of green roofs (Shin & Kim, 2015, 2019).

Table 5 summarizes CBA results, excluding nine observations for which results were not reported. In a few studies that analyse integrated NBS interventions, only the CBA outcome of the full intervention was reported, without separate results for the component NBS. These findings are presented in the table under the “combination of solutions” category. Combined CBAs were used, for example, to economically assess complete sustainable urban drainage systems (Johnson & Geisendorf, 2019), combined adaptation measures for urban heat islands (Johnson et al., 2020), or a combination of greening systems installed in an office building (Perini & Rosasco, 2016). Generally, most of the CBA results across all NBS types are positive. The sole exception is urban parks, for which only a single negative observation is included in our review. Green roofs (unspecified) and rain gardens were the only NBS categories for which more than 40 % of the observations reported negative outcomes.

Additionally, in cases where multiple CBAs were conducted, some studies reported mixed outcomes, presenting both positive and negative results. This was observed in cases where different configurations of costs and benefits were included in the evaluations. For example, the study from Shazmin & Zulkifli (2020), found a range of BCR values for extensive and intensive green roofs, which varied according to specific characteristics of the green roofs, such as substrate depth, type of vegetation and roof slope.

Finally, we examined whether and how the studies addressed uncertainty. Table 6 shows the number of observations for which uncertainty analysis was performed and the evaluated parameters. Uncertainty was assessed in the majority of cases (81), and was mainly addressed through Monte Carlo simulations. A small number of studies addressed uncertainty by estimating “optimistic” and “pessimistic” scenarios (Claus & Rousseau, 2012), or by calculating NPV using different discount rates (Dubová & Macháč, 2019; Locatelli et al., 2020). In general, uncertainty was addressed by varying key parameters such as the values of costs and benefits, the discount rate, and the input data used to estimate monetary values, such as water production (García-Herrero et al., 2022), stormwater charges (Johnson & Geisendorf, 2019), climate factors (Berto et al., 2018; Niu et al., 2010), and energy price volatility (Carter & Keeler, 2008). Specifically, costs and benefits were adjusted in sensitivity analyses, as they are usually approximations influenced by uncertainty (Claus & Rousseau, 2012). For the discount rate, sensitivity analysis was performed to examine its influence on the CBA result (Du et al., 2020; Teotónio et al., 2018).

3.3. Characteristics of benefits and costs valuation methods

Table A5 in the Supplementary Material shows the valuation approaches used to estimate benefit values. Value transfer was the most common methodology, particularly for including those benefits in the CBA that would otherwise be difficult to estimate. This method, however, has some limitations, in terms of requiring adjustment of transferred values to reflect the context of the study (Nordman et al., 2018). The use of market prices was mainly applied in the evaluation of provisioning ES, such as biomass and food provision (Begum et al., 2021; Schoen et al., 2020; Teotónio et al., 2018), or to estimate the increase in property value of buildings due to NBS (Rosasco & Perini, 2018). Among the cost-based approaches, the avoided cost method was the most frequently used, especially for estimating savings in buildings, such as avoided energy expenses due reduced heating and cooling demand (Almeida et al., 2021; Nurmi et al., 2016; Teotónio et al., 2018), or avoided costs of replacing building structures (Nurmi et al., 2016; Perini & Rosasco, 2016). In many instances, avoided cost method was also used to estimate the value of “regulation of water flow” benefit. In this case, the avoided cost represented the reduction in water management costs for municipalities or private owners (in terms of fee reduction) due to decreased water volumes entering the sewage system (Johnson & Geisendorf, 2019; Niu et al., 2010). The damage cost avoided method was used to assess the value of flood risk reduction by estimating the decrease in expected annual damage from flood events (Locatelli et al., 2020). It was also used to estimate the monetary value of the “improved mental and physical health” benefit, calculated as the savings resulting from the reduction in hospital admissions due to the impact of the urban heat island reduction caused by the presence of NBS (Johnson et al., 2020). Carbon pricing category, which include both the social cost of carbon and carbon taxes, has been extensively used to estimate the value of avoided air pollution and CO₂ emissions. Finally, the behavioral linkages method has been used in a few cases, mainly for estimating benefits related to cultural ES, such as aesthetic appreciation and increased recreation.

Table A6 in the Supplementary Material shows the sources of the costs monetary values. Typically, studies used the same method for estimating different categories of costs within the same CBA. Costs were mainly estimated by consulting academic literature (52 cases) and experts (29 cases), through interviews with companies and field specialists. In some instances, costs were estimated using more than one method. For example, academic literature and expert consultations were used simultaneously in 44 cases, while expert consultations and price lists were combined in 22 cases.

Table 7 presents the results of the spatial analysis of the benefits. We compared the spatial scale of NBS implementation with the spatial extent of the economic advantage derived from each benefit. The purpose is to identify whether NBS provide broader economic advantages than their implementation scale. Additional information can be found in Tables A7 of the Supplementary Material. 52 benefits were excluded from this analysis since their spatial distribution was not clearly identifiable. In general, the analysis indicates that the economic advantage

Table 3
Benefits distribution among the different types of NBS. Colors indicate NBS categories.

	BENEFITS																						
	Aesthetic appreciation	Air pollution emission reduction	Air pollution sequestration	Biodiversity increase	Biomass production	CO2 emission reduction	CO2 sequestration	Energy saving	Flood risk reduction	Food provision	Groundwater recharge	Increase infrastructure longevity	Increase property value	Increase recreation opportunities	Job creation	Local climate regulation	Mental and physical health	Noise reduction	Other benefits	Regulation of water flows	Subsidies and tax reduction	Wastewater treatment	Water provision
Intensive green roof (n = 7)	2	1	2	1		2	2	3	2	2		2	1		1	2		3	1	2	2	1	
Extensive green roof (n =19)	10	8	10	5		5	6	15	5			11	1			5	2	7		14	4	3	
Green roof (unspecified) (n =12)	5	4	5	1		4	2	6	7	1		4	2		1	2	4	1	2	7		1	
Green facade (n = 15)	11	5	9				1	3				9	1				2	9	4	1			
Green wall system (n = 15)	9	4	8		1		1	3				9	3					9	3		1		
Rain garden (n = 6)	3	2		1		1			5							1				3		4	
Infiltration basin (n = 5)	1							1	4		1		1	1						3	1	2	1
Retention pond (n = 4)	1		1	1		1			3					1						2	2	2	1
Swale (n = 5)									1		4									5			
Vegetated grid pave (n = 8)		1				1		1	5		2					1	2		1	4	1	3	
Low vegetation (n = 1)																	2		1	1			
Urban park (n =1)														1									
Use of pre-existing vegetation (n =1)	1		1				1		1											1		1	
Street trees (n = 6)	2		6			1	5	2	1		1		1				4			5		1	
Woodlands and groups of trees (n = 2)													1						1				
Community garden (n = 4)	2		3		1		2	1		2					1	1	1		3	2	1	2	
Constructed wetland (n = 3)							1		2										1			1	1

■ Building solutions
 ■ Bioretention areas
 ■ Open green spaces
 ■ Urban forests
 ■ Urban farming
 ■ Constructed wetlands

Table 4
Costs distribution among the different types of NBS. Colors indicate NBS categories.

	COSTS							
	Investment	Operation and maintenance	Opportunity	Environmental	Residual	Removal	Replacement	Other
Intensive green roof (n = 7)	7	5		2		2	3	
Extensive green roof (n = 19)	19	16		3	1	3	5	4
Green roof (unspecified) (n = 12)	12	10		1	1	1	1	
Green facade (n = 15)	15	15		4		5	12	
Green wall system (n = 15)	15	15		4		7	11	
Rain garden (n = 6)	6	5	2		2			
Infiltration basin (n = 5)	5	5			1			1
Retention pond (n = 4)	4	3			1			
Swale (n = 5)	5	5						
Vegetated grid pave (n = 8)	8	7						
Low vegetation (n = 1)	1	1						
Urban park (n = 1)	1							
Use of pre-existing vegetation (n = 1)			1					
Street trees (n = 6)	4	4						
Woodlands and groups of trees (n = 2)	1	1	2					
Community garden (n = 4)	4	4						
Constructed wetland (n = 3)	3	1						

provided by the benefits usually aligns with the spatial scale of NBS implementation. However, in some instances, the benefits extend to wider scales. For example, aesthetic enhancements resulting from site-specific interventions (9 cases)—such as the implementation of buildings solution on an underground passage (Melo et al., 2020), or on an industrial building (Berto et al., 2018), and the creation of a community garden (Dubová & Macháč, 2019) —were evaluated as increases in the real estate values of buildings located in the surroundings of these interventions. Another example is regulation of the water flow benefit provided by NBS implemented at the site or neighborhood scale. In many cases, this service has been recognized for its economic contribution at the city scale and quantified in terms of cost savings for the municipality, as NBS reduce the need of water treatment and drainage system infrastructures. Other benefits that fall under the broader spatial scale are air pollutant emission reductions, groundwater recharge, and wastewater treatment. A particular case is CO₂ emission reduction and sequestration benefit, that is predominantly assessed at the global level.

Finally, Table A8 of the Supplementary Material shows the temporal distribution of the CBA benefits. Ten benefits observations were omitted due to unspecified CBA time frames. Benefits were accounted for annually throughout the entire CBA time horizon in nearly all the studies, and none of them considered effects beyond the infrastructure’s lifespan. Exceptions were observed in some studies on building solutions. Specifically, aesthetic appreciation was, in certain instances, included only in the initial year of the CBA, particularly when it was assessed in terms of increased property values, signifying an immediate

capitalization of the benefit. Likewise, benefits associated with enhanced infrastructure longevity, such as those arising from green roofs, were typically considered only in the year when roof renovation was avoided. Another exception can be found in the study by Teotónio et al., (2018) where the value of flood risk reduction was estimated as an avoided cost of a planned intervention in Lisbon. The benefit was considered for the same years as the intervention was planned (annually until the 15th year). Similarly, urban noise reduction was estimated as an avoided cost and considered only in the years when the noise mitigation intervention was scheduled (years 1, 6 and 10). These time lags, however, do not depend on the time required for the ES to be provided in full but, in contrast, are related to the valuation approach adopted. In this regard, the study by Rosasco & Perini (2018) is noteworthy for estimating the value of biomass production starting from the 4th year post-installation.

4. Discussion

4.1. CBA types, purposes and spatial scales

Our review shows that most CBA studies on NBS have employed a social CBA approach. This trend likely stems from the inherent nature of NBS, which generate both positive and negative impacts not only for direct investors but also for the broader community. The reviewed studies stress the importance of including these impacts in economic evaluations to give decision-makers a comprehensive perspective (Benis

Table 5
Distribution of the CBA outcomes for each NBS type.

	OUTCOMES		
	Positive	Negative	Mixed
Intensive green roof (n = 6)	4	1	1
Extensive green roof (n = 12)	9	2	1
Green roof (unspecified) (n = 10)	6	4	
Green facade (n = 13)	12	1	
Green wall system (n = 14)	12	2	
Rain garden (n = 5)	3	2	
Infiltration basin (n = 3)	3		
Retention pond (n = 2)	2		
Swale (n = 1)			1
Vegetated grid pave (n = 4)	3	1	
Urban park (n = 1)		1	
Use of pre-existing vegetation (n = 1)	1		
Street trees (n = 3)	3		
Woodlands and groups of trees (n = 2)	2		
Community garden (n = 4)	4		
Constructed wetland (n = 3)	3		
Combination of solutions (n = 5)	4		4

Table 6
Uncertainty analysis and parameters evaluated for each NBS type.

	NUMBER OF OBS. WITH UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS	UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS PARAMETERS			
		Costs	Benefits	Cost/Benefit inputs	Discount rate
Intensive green roof (n = 7)	4	4	4		1
Extensive green roof (n = 19)	13	12	11	4	6
Green roof (unspecified) (n = 12)	7	5	5	1	5
Green facade (n = 15)	15	15	15	2	10
Green wall system (n = 15)	15	15	15		8
Rain garden (n = 6)	5	3	3	1	2
Infiltration basin (n = 5)	1	1	1		1
Retention pond (n = 4)	2	1	1	1	2
Swale (n = 5)	3	3	3	3	3
Vegetated grid pave (n = 8)	3	3	3	1	2
Low vegetation (n = 1)	1	1	1		1
Urban park (n = 1)					
Use of pre-existing vegetation (n = 1)	1	1	1		
Street trees (n = 6)	4	4	4	2	3
Woodlands and groups of trees (n = 2)	2	1	1	2	
Community garden (n = 4)	2	1			2
Constructed wetland (n = 3)	2	1		1	2

■ Building solutions
 ■ Bioretention areas
 ■ Open green spaces
 ■ Urban forests
 ■ Urban farming
 ■ Constructed wetlands

et al., 2018). Excluding them could lead to economic assessments that undervalue the intervention's benefits. For instance, Berto et al. (2018) compared the economic feasibility of green and cool roofs, showing that while cool roofs are more cost-effective from a private standpoint, green roofs yield better outcomes when social CBA is applied. Similarly, multi-level CBA studies on building solutions by Almeida et al. (2021), Matos Silva et al. (2019), Melo et al. (2020), and Teotónio et al. (2018) found generally negative results when only financial costs and benefits were considered. However, when economic, social and environmental impacts were accounted for, the outcomes turned favorable.

Private CBA is, however, essential to determine the direct profitability of the project for the investor, particularly when NBS are implemented on private properties. Private individuals who decide to implement NBS on their properties are often more interested in understanding the direct costs and benefits to themselves rather than the broader economic impact on society. Nevertheless, complementing private CBA with social CBA can be useful in assessing the public value of an investment and could encourage the development of public policies and incentives to promote the adoption of NBS by private property owners. For example, Berto et al. (2018) conducted both private and social CBA and highlighted that monetizing social externalities helped determine the economic incentives needed to promote green roof adoption. An alternative approach to including social and environmental externalities in the economic evaluation of NBS could be to complement private CBA with a non-economic evaluation (e.g., biophysical or qualitative assessment) of the social impacts of NBS, as shown in the studies by Perini & Rosasco (2016). This approach ensures that the environmental and social externalities of NBS are still considered in decision-making, even if not expressed in monetary terms. Conducting a social CBA, however, is undoubtedly more complex than a private CBA, as many of the benefits and costs involved are challenging to quantify in monetary terms. This complexity could lead to a preference for private CBAs in practice or social CBAs that omit certain

benefits and costs of NBS.

Our results show that the CBA literature has predominantly focused on specific types of NBS, especially building solutions and bioretention areas. One reason is that such studies often performed CBA on multiple NBS, which we treated as individual observations. Studies on other types of NBS, however, are generally lacking. We encourage future CBA research to focus on these less-explored NBS types to provide more evidence of their economic feasibility.

Our review supports the existing literature, demonstrating that the main purpose of CBA of NBS is to assess the economic viability of different investment options (Locatelli et al., 2020). In this context, CBA was mainly used to compare solutions aimed at addressing specific urban challenges, such as mitigating heat waves and urban heat island effects (Zhang & Ayyub, 2020a), or urban flooding (Shazmin & Zulkifli, 2020; Wang et al., 2021). In these cases, CBA can be complemented by cost-effectiveness analysis, which assesses the cost of achieving a specific outcome (Graveline & Calatrava, 2017; Lopez Gunn et al., 2023). Our analysis shows that CBA is commonly used to compare NBS with traditional technical interventions. Unlike grey solutions, NBS generally provide additional social and environmental co-benefits that generate economic advantages. Excluding these co-benefits from the CBA can bias the analysis toward technical solutions. For instance, Alves et al. (2019) assessed the economic feasibility of green, blue, and grey infrastructures for managing urban flood risks. Their findings showed that excluding co-benefits made grey infrastructure the only economically viable option, emphasizing the need to include co-benefits in CBA for a complete evaluation. Using CBA on existing NBS can also provide valuable insights. For example, Soares et al. (2011) and McPherson (2003) estimated the economic value of trees in Lisbon and Washington DC, respectively. These assessments highlight the value of natural assets in urban areas, raising awareness among citizens and stakeholders, and encouraging public support for integrating these assets into urban planning.

Table 7
Spatial distribution of the benefits according to the spatial scale of NBS implementation.

	Dominant spatial scale of NBS implementation	Dominant spatial scale of benefits value estimation	Proportion of benefits evaluated at the same spatial scale as NBS implementation
Aesthetic appreciation (n = 44)	Site	Site	80%
Air pollutant emission reduction (n = 14)	District	City	57%
Air pollution sequestration (n = 19)	Site	Site	100%
Biodiversity increase (n = 8)	City	City	88%
Biomass production (n = 2)	Site	Site	100%
CO2 emission reduction (n = 9)	City & District	Global	0%
CO2 sequestration (n = 20)	Neighborhood	Global	0%
Energy saving (n = 34)	Site	Site	100%
Flood risk reduction (n = 35)	District	District	83%
Food provision (n = 6)	Site	Site	100%
Groundwater recharge (n = 8)	Neighborhood	City	25%
Increase infrastructure longevity (n = 35)	Site	Site	100%
Increase property value (n = 11)	Site	Site	100%
Increase recreation opportunities (n = 3)	Neighborhood	Neighborhood	100%
Job creation (n = 1)	Neighborhood	Neighborhood	100%
Local climate regulation (n = 10)	City	City	100%
Mental and physical health (n = 17)	City	City	100%
Noise reduction (n = 29)	Site	Site	76%
Regulation of water flows (n = 47)	Neighborhood	City	62%
Subsidies and tax reduction (n = 12)	Site	Site	83%
Wastewater treatment (n = 21)	Neighborhood	City	43%
Water provision (n = 3)	District	District	100%

It is important to consider the spatial scale of NBS when conducting CBA, as it can impact the type and magnitude of costs and benefits produced by the solution. Some benefits are scale-dependent and can only be realized at specific spatial scales (Raymond et al., 2017). Additionally, costs vary with the scale of implementation, influenced by factors such as project size, site-specific conditions, and economies of scale (Bianchini & Hewage, 2012). In the literature, CBA has been applied to NBS implemented at various spatial scales, with site level being the most frequently analyzed category. This predominance may be due to factors such as funding limitations, spatial constraints, or policy frameworks that favor the implementation of smaller NBS, that are usually more manageable. An exception to this trend is bioretention NBS, for which site-level CBA has not been conducted. These solutions are typically designed for applications at a neighborhood or district scale (World Bank, 2021). In particular, in the reviewed studies, they have been usually implemented in conjunction with other NBS as part of comprehensive strategies aimed at reaching specific adaptation objectives or as part of the urban drainage system at the neighborhood, district, or city-wide levels. Given these results, we recommend more research on CBA of NBS applied at larger scales, as well as studies that

compare single site-level interventions with their scaled-up counterparts. These studies could provide evidence on potential economies of scale in the implementation of larger interventions compared to smaller ones.

4.2. Discount rate and temporal horizon

Our findings reveal substantial variability in the discount rates and temporal horizons used in CBA estimates. The variation in discount rates across studies often reflects the socio-economic conditions of each project. The selection of the discount rate is a crucial decision in CBA, particularly for initiatives with high initial costs and long-term benefits (Moore et al., 2013). A lower discount rate assigns greater weight to benefits realized further in the future, thereby increasing the likelihood that the benefits will outweigh the upfront costs. This can also influence project rankings, favoring those with substantial long-term benefits (Annema & Koopmans, 2015; Zhuang et al., 2007). The debate on the appropriate discount rate is ongoing, especially when considering social discounting for public investments with long-term impacts, such as initiatives targeting climate change and environmental concerns like

NBS (OECD, 2018). In the context of green infrastructure, the European Commission recommended a discount rate of 5 % for Cohesion Countries and 3 % for other Member States during the 2014–2020 programming period (European Commission, 2015a). Some of the reviewed studies adopted varying discount rates. For instance, Johnson et al. (2021) used a dual discounting approach, applying a 3 % discount rate for private costs and benefits and 2.1 % for social benefits, in line with recent literature suggesting this rate is suitable for discounting ES. Other studies, such as those by Berto et al. (2018), and Dumenu (2013) employed a declining discount rate, often used for assessing long-term impacts (Johnson et al., 2021). Several authors suggest that the correct social discount rate should vary over time to account for uncertainty in social CBA (Dumenu, 2013).

In some cases, the choice of the temporal horizon has a more significant impact than the discount rate (Defrancesco et al., 2014). Our results show that different temporal horizons have been used across studies, generally revealing an inclination towards long-term evaluation. Most CBAs limit their assessment to the expected lifespan of the NBS. However, in social CBA, it is advisable to extend this time frame to account for long-lasting environmental benefits or externalities. O'Mahony, (2021) suggests that for projects with enduring environmental impacts, such as those related to air pollution or climate change, an evaluation period exceeding 100 years should be employed. This implies that the environmental benefits should continue to be accounted for even after the infrastructure has reached the end of its useful life (OECD, 2018; O'Mahony, 2021). This extended temporal consideration has not been adequately addressed in the existing literature, highlighting a gap that warrants further research.

4.3. Costs and benefits considered, outcomes, and uncertainty

Assessing the value of NBS costs and benefits is generally more challenging than that of technical solutions (Sandin et al., 2022). While the cost assessments across the reviewed studies are generally consistent, there is considerable variability in how the benefits are accounted for. Almost all reviewed studies included both implementation and maintenance costs. These are the main costs associated with NBS. Maintenance costs are crucial for sustaining the long-term benefits of NBS (World Bank, 2021), and some types of NBS may require high management and maintenance costs, which must be carefully considered in the evaluation (Melo et al., 2020; Sandin et al., 2022). Additionally, only a few studies, particularly those related to building solutions, included the environmental externalities produced by NBS in their cost assessments. These externalities arise from the production, structure, and operation of materials used (Benis et al., 2018; García-Herrero et al., 2022; Melo et al., 2020; Vincent et al., 2017). The inclusion of environmental externalities is essential to account not only for the benefits of enhanced ecosystem services but also for the costs associated with ecosystem degradation (Gómez-Baggethun & Barton, 2013). The lack of consideration of negative environmental impacts in urban NBS has been already highlighted by many scholars (Babí Almenar et al., 2023; Keeler et al., 2019; Larrey-Lassalle et al., 2022). Some of the reviewed studies acknowledge the limitation of not considering environmental costs. For example, Berto et al. (2018) suggested that considering all life cycle phases in terms of potential environmental impacts and monetization would have enhanced the analysis. Zhou et al. (2013) stated that environmental costs were not considered due to a lack of information, and that considering these costs could have impacted their results. We encourage future research to consider these types of costs in their analyses and explore how their inclusion impacts the overall CBA outcomes. In this context, examining the impact of environmental costs when comparing NBS to technical solutions would be valuable. Technical solutions might appear more cost-effective in the short term, but in the long run, their significant environmental impact can make them more costly. Therefore, understanding the role of these costs is crucial when comparing different solutions to ensure a

comprehensive and accurate assessment. Finally, other authors highlight the uncertainty related to cost estimates (McPherson, 2003) and the use of outdated data sources, emphasizing the need for updated research on NBS costs (Johnson et al., 2020).

Our review indicates inconsistencies in the benefits included in the CBA of the same type of NBS, even in cases that are implemented at the same spatial scale. Although CBA aims to capture all welfare impacts, it often falls short, especially in accounting for specific environmental and social benefits. This finding aligns with existing literature, which emphasizes that the multiple benefits of NBS are often inadequately reflected in CBA (Neumann & Hack, 2022; Sandin et al., 2022). Authors of the reviewed studies have acknowledged this limitation, primarily attributing it to data scarcity and the complexity of quantifying and monetizing certain types of benefits, and stressed the need for further research to fill this gap (Alves et al., 2019; Berto et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2016; Peng & Jim, 2015; Yao et al., 2018). Some studies have addressed this challenge by evaluating certain benefits, such as increased water quality and biodiversity, qualitatively (Benis et al., 2018; Wilbers, 2022). This approach allows for the recognition of these positive effects in the evaluation, even when they are not monetized. Another option is to complement CBA with alternative evaluation methods that do not require monetary valuation, such as cost-effectiveness analysis, cost-impact analysis, and multi-criteria decision-making analysis (Melo et al., 2020; Wilbers, 2022). Zhou et al. (2013), for example, evaluated different flood mitigation strategies using a cross-disciplinary model that integrates risk assessment techniques, flood inundation modeling, climate change projections, environmental evaluation tools, and socio-economic tools. They argued that a CBA approach is insufficient as a decision-making tool because it overlooks potential positive and negative non-market services provided by these solutions. Based on these findings, we recommend further research to develop more comprehensive economic evaluation frameworks for NBS. Furthermore, conducting a CBA on NBS often requires interdisciplinary collaboration, which can be challenging to implement, limiting the inclusion of all potential benefits. Even when environmental and social benefits have been monetized, some studies have identified limitations due to uncertainties in the estimates. These uncertainties were associated with the monetary valuation techniques employed, data availability, incomplete information, and assumptions applied in the analysis (Alves et al., 2019; Chabba et al., 2022; Claus & Rousseau, 2012; Nordman et al., 2018).

It is crucial to acknowledge that even if some analyses did not capture the full range of benefits, the general economic performance of CBAs tends to be positive in most of the reviewed studies. This observation highlights the potential for NBS to achieve higher economic outcomes if analyses fully accounted for all benefits. All types of NBS showed a tendency to yield positive CBA outcomes. However, the predominance of positive over negative CBA outcomes could be influenced by publication bias, which may lead to a tendency to publish studies with favorable results. In this context, we advocate for the dissemination of all empirical findings, both positive and negative, to foster a nuanced understanding of the factors determining success and failure in NBS projects and to inform the design of future interventions.

Most reviewed studies addressed uncertainty by performing sensitivity analysis. Sensitivity analysis evaluates the robustness of the results when parameters change (Hanley & Spash, 1993). It is crucial in CBA due to the high level of uncertainty in most parameter estimates. Some studies demonstrated that changes in parameters can significantly influence CBA outcomes. For instance, Almeida et al. (2021) indicates that a 10 % variation in some cost and benefit categories leads to a 4 % to 10 % change in the estimated BCR. Conversely, other studies showed minimal impact from parameter changes. For example, García-Herrero et al. (2022) found that modifying the discount rate, maintenance costs, and water output led to only minimal variations in the outcomes of the analysis. Some studies found that results are sensitive to specific parameters only. For instance, Johnson & Geisendorf, (2019) showed that outcomes are sensitive to private cost and benefit parameters, but not to

social ones. Especially in the context of CBA studies comparing NBS and technical solutions, we encourage further research to explore how economic efficiency comparisons change when uncertainty is addressed. This is particularly important because technical solutions are generally considered more certain than NBS.

4.4. Benefit valuation methods

Our results show that similar benefit types were often monetised using the same valuation approach or through the value transfer method. This aligns with the literature, as the choice of valuation methodology is typically influenced by the type of benefit being considered (García-Herrero et al., 2022). The most frequently used valuation methods were cost-based approaches and value transfer. Value transfer is particularly useful when quick and inexpensive estimations are needed, though its adoption should be approached with caution (Brander, 2013). Our findings are consistent with existing literature, confirming the popularity of this method in Europe within the context of CBA (Johnston et al., 2015). Some studies, however, highlight the use of value transfer as a limitation, as transferring values from one context to another may result in estimation errors (Nordman et al., 2018). The valuation approach significantly affects the estimated economic value, highlighting the need for a contextually relevant methodology (Brander, 2013). It can also have implications for policy decisions. Stakeholders may have different preferences regarding the type of economic benefit they aim to gain from NBS. Some may prioritize direct revenue generation, while others may place greater value on cost avoidance. Therefore, it is important to select a valuation method that takes these preferences into account, as they can significantly influence the level of investment and political support for specific NBS. Given the limited existing research on stakeholder preferences for different types of economic benefits, further investigation in this area is needed.

The spatial distribution of NBS benefits depends on numerous factors. These include the type of NBS, the scale at which it is implemented, and the nature of the impact under consideration (Raymond, 2017). Additionally, the evaluation is influenced by the biological and physical mechanisms governing benefit provision, and the spatial distribution of stakeholders (van Zanten et al., 2023). Our review reveals that benefits are mainly assessed within the implementation site, and, in some cases, extend to broader scales. This alignment may result from factors such as ease of measurement and direct cause-effect relationships within the same spatial context. When small-scale NBS interventions were found to provide broader economic benefits, these benefits were often considered public. An example is the water flow regulation benefit generated by small-scale NBS, where its value was often estimated as a reduction in urban water management costs at the city level. The idea that broader-scale benefits serve as public goods raises important questions, such as who should bear the costs of such interventions and how to incentivize private investments. This also raises social equity issues, as non-investors still benefit from the NBS. Moreover, the distribution of benefits across spatial scales can influence NBS decision-making. Projects delivering multi-scale benefits might be more likely to attract greater investment and policy support.

Although this review could not assess the spatial extent of the costs due to a lack of information in the reviewed studies, we recognize that certain costs, especially those related to environmental externalities, may be borne by stakeholders far from where NBS are implemented and may also be delayed in time (Babí Almenar et al., 2023; Pascual et al., 2017). This can result in an unequal distribution of NBS benefits and costs within society. We encourage further research to investigate the different spatial distributions of costs and benefits from NBS. This research should consider mapping the lifecycle impacts of NBS and evaluating their geographical distribution, ensuring that the benefits of NBS are not concentrated in certain communities while costs are unfairly imposed on others.

Finally, our review found that studies did not explicitly address the

temporal distribution of benefits. According to O'Mahony (2021), benefits from projects with an environmental impact can manifest immediately upon the infrastructure implementation, be delayed, or even extend beyond the technical lifespan of the project. Most analyses assumed full delivery of benefits from the first year of the CBA, extending this assumption throughout the infrastructure's lifespan. In addition, they did not consider that some benefits might persist even beyond the end of the NBS's operational lifespan, potentially underestimating long-term impacts. In the few cases where benefits were only accounted for in specific years, these delays were not due to the capacity of the ES to be fully effective but were instead related to the valuation approach used. It is important to note, however, that the realization of some benefits from NBS may take time. Examples from the Nature4Cities initiative indicate that urban parks usually take between 1 and 5 years to become fully effective. Some benefits, such as those related to air quality, social habits, and health, can take up to 15 years to fully materialize. Similarly, urban forests and street trees can require up to 10 years to reach full effectiveness, depending on factors such as species and growth properties (Nature4Cities, 2018). Our findings align with existing literature. Hein et al. (2016) emphasized that temporal changes in ES values are often neglected in CBA for ecosystem management and natural capital accounting. Our review confirms this trend in the context of urban NBS. Given the long-term responses of ecosystems to management interventions, these temporal changes are highly relevant. Therefore, practitioners using CBA should be mindful of both the temporal fluctuations in ecosystem values and the uncertainties arising from them. Further research in the CBA of NBS should consider the temporal distribution of the benefits. This involves acknowledging and integrating the diverse timeframes within which these benefits materialize, thereby ensuring that CBAs better reflect actual impacts.

4.5. Limitations of the study

The scope of this study is limited by the keywords used in the search, which may influence the findings. To address this, we expanded our search criteria to include terms specific to NBS as well as those related to green infrastructure more broadly. Despite this, some relevant studies may have been overlooked. Secondly, our search was limited to publications indexed in Scopus and Web of Science, excluding grey literature, which may contain valuable case studies. In addition, some reviewed studies lacked information on all elements addressed in our study. As a result, these observations were excluded from certain analyses, resulting in potential gaps in our findings.

Some assumptions were made regarding the categorization of information from the reviewed papers when not clearly reported, particularly concerning the spatial scale of NBS, monetary valuation methods, and spatial and temporal distribution of benefits. For example, when the spatial scale of an intervention was unclear, we inferred it based on the size of the intervention if this information was available. Similarly, when the temporal horizon of benefits was not specified, we assumed it to be the same as the CBA temporal horizon.

Finally, another limitation of our study is the omission of an analysis of the spatial and temporal distribution of costs. Despite its relevance to decision making, this aspect was not addressed due to a lack of information in the reviewed literature. Future research could benefit from a detailed examination of the spatial distribution of both costs and benefits of NBS, as such an analysis would provide a more comprehensive understanding of their economic impacts on society.

5. Conclusions

The objective of our study was to provide an overview of the applications of CBA to urban NBS through a systematic review, identifying the main trends, limitations, and research gaps. We focused on specific aspects of CBA to evaluate the coherence of approaches across different studies and examined the methodologies employed for benefit and costs

valuation, and the temporal and spatial distributions of benefits.

Some patterns emerged from our analysis, such as the predominance of social CBA and a focus on analyzing building solutions and small-scale NBS interventions. Moreover, we found a general lack of consideration for environmental externalities among the costs, and an incomplete inclusion of the full range of benefits, generally due to difficulties in estimating their monetary values. A lack of consideration of the temporal dynamics of benefits within the CBA was also identified. We acknowledge the complexities and interdisciplinary nature of performing economic analyses of NBS and offer some recommendations for future research. We also propose the expansion of CBA assessments to a wider variety of NBS that have not yet been extensively studied, such as urban forests, community gardens, and open green spaces. Researchers should consider extending the temporal horizon of their assessments beyond the lifespan of the NBS to fully capture their social and environmental impacts, as well as considering the temporal variation of benefits. Finally, efforts should be made to incorporate a more comprehensive range of co-benefits and costs, especially negative environmental and social externalities, to accurately reflect the true value of NBS.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alessia Chelli: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Luke Brander:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Davide Geneletti:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

DG and LB acknowledge support from SELINA project. SELINA receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060415. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. AC acknowledge support from the SUSTEEMS PhD programme of the University of Trento.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2024.101684>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

Adem Esmail, B., Geneletti, D., 2018. Multi-criteria decision analysis for nature conservation: A review of 20 years of applications. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 9 (1), 42–53. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12899>.

Aerts, J.C.J.H., Botzen, W.J.W., Emanuel, K., Lin, N., de Moel, H., Michel-Kerjan, E.O., 2014. Evaluating Flood Resilience Strategies for Coastal Megacities. *Science* 344 (6183), 473–475. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1248222>.

Aevermann, T., Schmude, J., 2015. Quantification and monetary valuation of urban ecosystem services in Munich, Germany. *Zeitschrift Für Wirtschaftsgeographie* 59 (3), 188–200. <https://doi.org/10.1515/zfw-2015-0304>.

Almeida, C., Teotônio, I., Silva, C.M., Cruz, C.O., 2021. Socioeconomic feasibility of green roofs and walls in public buildings: The case study of primary schools in

Portugal. *Eng. Econ.* 66 (1), 27–50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0013791X.2020.1748255>.

Alves, A., Gersonius, B., Kapelan, Z., Vojinovic, Z., Sanchez, A., 2019. Assessing the Co-Benefits of green-blue-grey infrastructure for sustainable urban flood risk management. *J. Environ. Manage.* 239, 244–254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.03.036>.

Annema, J.A., Koopmans, C., 2015. The practice of valuing the environment in cost-benefit analyses in transport and spatial projects. *J. Environ. Plan. Manag.* 58 (9), 1635–1648. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2014.941975>.

Arrow, K.J., Cropper, M.L., Eads, G.C., Hahn, R.W., Lave, L.B., Noll, R.G., Portney, P.R., Russell, M., Schmalensee, R., Smith, V.K., Stavins, R.N., 1997. Is there a role for benefit-cost analysis in environmental, health, and safety regulation? *Environ. Dev. Econ.* 2 (2), 195–221. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1355770X97220164>.

Asplund, D., Eliasson, J., 2016. Does uncertainty make cost-benefit analyses pointless? *Transp. Res. A Policy Pract.* 92, 195–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2016.08.002>.

Babí Almenar, J., Petucco, C., Sonnemann, G., Geneletti, D., Elliot, T., Rugani, B., 2023. Modelling the net environmental and economic impacts of urban nature-based solutions by combining ecosystem services, system dynamics and life cycle thinking: An application to urban forests. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 60, 101506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2022.101506>.

Begum, M.S., Bala, S.K., Islam, A.K.M.S., Roy, D., 2021. Environmental and Social Dynamics of Urban Rooftop Agriculture (URTA) and Their Impacts on Microclimate Change. *Sustainability* 13 (16). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169053>.

Benis, K., Turan, I., Reinhart, C., Ferrão, P., 2018. Putting rooftops to use – A Cost-Benefit Analysis of food production vs. Energy Generation under Mediterranean Climates. *Cities* 78, 166–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2018.02.011>.

Berto, R., Stival, C.A., Rosato, P., 2018. Enhancing the environmental performance of industrial settlements: An economic evaluation of extensive green roof competitiveness. *Build. Environ.* 127, 58–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2017.10.032>.

A.E. Boardman D.H. Greenberg A.R. Vining D.L. Weimer Cost-Benefit Analysis: Concepts and Practice (5a ed.). 2018 Cambridge University Press 10.1017/9781108235594.

L. Brander P. Van Beukering M. Balzan S. Broekx I. Liekens C. Marta-Pedroso Z. Szkop J. Vause J. Maes F. Santos-Martin M. Potschin-Young Report on Economic Mapping and Assessment Methods for Ecosystem Services 2018.

Carter, T., Keeler, A., 2008. Life-cycle cost-benefit analysis of extensive vegetated roof systems. *J. Environ. Manage.* 87 (3), 350–363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2007.01.024>.

Castañer, C.M., Bellver-Domingo, Á., Hernández-Sancho, F., 2020. Environmental and Economic Approach to Assess a Horizontal Sub-Surface Flow Wetland in Developing Area. *Water Resour. Manag.* 34 (12), 3761–3778. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-020-02629-x>.

Castellar, J.A.C., Popartan, L.A., Pueyo-Ros, J., Atanasova, N., Langergraber, G., Säumel, I., Corominas, L., Comas, J., Acuña, V., 2021. Nature-based solutions in the urban context: Terminology, classification and scoring for urban challenges and ecosystem services. *Sci. Total Environ.* 779, 146237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.146237>.

Chabba, M., Bhat, M.G., Sarmiento, J.P., 2022. Risk-based benefit-cost analysis of ecosystem-based disaster risk reduction with considerations of co-benefits, equity, and sustainability. *Ecol. Econ.* 198, 107462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107462>.

Claus, K., Rousseau, S., 2012. Public versus private incentives to invest in green roofs: A cost benefit analysis for Flanders. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 11 (4), 417–425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2012.07.003>.

Cortinovis, C., Geneletti, D., 2019. A framework to explore the effects of urban planning decisions on regulating ecosystem services in cities. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 38, 100946. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.100946>.

Defrancesco, E., Gatto, P., Rosato, P., 2014. A 'component-based' approach to discounting for natural resource damage assessment. *Ecol. Econ.* 99, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2013.12.017>.

Di Pirro, E., Roebeling, P., Sallustio, L., Marchetti, M., Lasserre, B., 2023. Cost-Effectiveness of Nature-Based Solutions under Different Implementation Scenarios: A National Perspective for Italian Urban Areas. *Land* 12 (3), 603. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land12030603>.

Drupp, M.A., Freeman, M.C., Groom, B., Nesje, F., 2018. Discounting disentangled. *Am. Econ. J. Econ. Pol.* 10 (4), 109–134.

Du, S., Scussolini, P., Ward, P., Zhang, M., Wen, J., Wang, L., Koks, E., Diaz Loaiza, M., Gao, J., Ke, Q., Aerts, J., 2020. Hard or soft flood adaptation? Advantages of a hybrid strategy for Shanghai. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 61, 102037. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2020.102037>.

Dubová, L., Macháč, J., 2019. Improving the quality of life in cities using community gardens: From benefits for members to benefits for all local residents. *GeoScape* 13 (1), 68–78. <https://doi.org/10.2478/geosc-2019-0005>.

Dumenu, W.K., 2013. What are we missing? Economic value of an urban forest in Ghana. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 5, 137–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2013.07.001>.

Elliot, T., Babí Almenar, J., Niza, S., Proença, V., Rugani, B., 2019. Pathways to Modelling Ecosystem Services within an Urban Metabolism Framework. *Sustainability* 11 (10), 2766. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11102766>.

Escobedo, F.J., Kroeger, T., Wagner, J.E., 2011. Urban forests and pollution mitigation: Analyzing ecosystem services and disservices. *Environ. Pollut.* 159 (8–9), 2078–2087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2011.01.010>.

García-Herrero, L., Lavrnić, S., Guerrieri, V., Toscano, A., Milani, M., Cirelli, G.L., Vittuari, M., 2022. Cost-benefit of green infrastructures for water management: A sustainability assessment of full-scale constructed wetlands in Northern and

- Southern Italy. *Ecol. Eng.* 185, 106797. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoeng.2022.106797>.
- Geneletti, D., & Ferretti, V. (2015). Multicriteria analysis for sustainability assessment: Concepts and case studies (pp. 235–264). <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783471379.00019>.
- Giordano, R., Pluchinotta, L., Pagano, A., Scricieci, A., Nanu, F., 2020. Enhancing nature-based solutions acceptance through stakeholders' engagement in co-benefits identification and trade-offs analysis. *Sci. Total Environ.* 713, 136552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.136552>.
- Godyn, I., 2022. Economic Incentives in Stormwater Management: A Study of Practice Gaps in Poland. *Water* 14, 3817. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14233817>.
- Graveline, N., Calatrava, J., 2017. General framework for the economic assessment of Nature Based Solutions and their insurance value - NAIAD project deliverable 4.1 «NAture Insurance value. Assessment and Demonstration».
- Haghighatafshar, S., Nordlöf, B., Roldin, M., Gustafsson, L.-G., La Cour Jansen, J., Jönsson, K., 2018. Efficiency of blue-green stormwater retrofits for flood mitigation—Conclusions drawn from a case study in Malmö, Sweden. *J. Environ. Manage.* 207, 60–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.11.018>.
- Hanley, N., Spash, C.L., 1993. *Cost-Benefit Analysis and the Environment*.
- Hansjürgens, B., 2004. Economic valuation through cost-benefit analysis? Possibilities and Limitations. *Toxicology* 205 (3), 241–252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tox.2004.06.054>.
- Hein, L., van Koppen, C.S.A., (Kris), van Ierland, E. C., & Leidekker, J., 2016. Temporal scales, ecosystem dynamics, stakeholders and the valuation of ecosystems services. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 21, 109–119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2016.07.008>.
- Johnson, D., Exl, J., Geisendorf, S., 2021. The Potential of Stormwater Management in Addressing the Urban Heat Island Effect: An Economic Valuation. *Sustainability* 13 (16), 8685. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13168685>.
- Johnson, D., Geisendorf, S., 2019. Are Neighborhood-level SUDS Worth it? An Assessment of the Economic Value of Sustainable Urban Drainage System Scenarios Using Cost-Benefit Analyses. *Ecol. Econ.* 158, 194–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2018.12.024>.
- Johnson, D., See, L.M., Oswald, S.M., Prokop, G., Krisztin, T., 2020. A cost-benefit analysis of implementing urban heat island adaptation measures in small- and medium-sized cities in Austria. *Environ. Plann. B: Urban Anal. City Sci.* <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399808320974689>.
- Kabisch, N., Frantzeskaki, N., Pautleit, S., Naumann, S., Davis, M., Artmann, M., Haase, D., Knapp, S., Korn, H., Stadler, J., Zaunberger, K., Bonn, A., 2016. Nature-based solutions to climate change mitigation and adaptation in urban areas: Perspectives on indicators, knowledge gaps, barriers, and opportunities for action. *Ecol. Soc.* 21 (2). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-08373-210239>.
- Keeler, B.L., Hamel, P., McPherson, T., Hamann, M.H., Donahue, M.L., Meza Prado, K.A., Arkema, K.K., Bratman, G.N., Brauman, K.A., Finlay, J.C., Guerry, A.D., Hobbie, S.E., Johnson, J.A., MacDonald, G.K., McDonald, R.I., Neverisky, N., Wood, S.A., 2019. Social-ecological and technological factors moderate the value of urban nature. *Nat. Sustainability* 2 (1), 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0202-1>.
- Larrey-Lassalle, P., Armand Decker, S., Perfido, D., Naneci, S., Rugani, B., 2022. Life Cycle Assessment Applied to Nature-Based Solutions: Learnings, Methodological Challenges, and Perspectives from a Critical Analysis of the Literature. *Land* 11 (5), 649. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land111050649>.
- Le Coent, P., Graveline, N., Altamirano, M.A., Arfaoui, N., Benitez-Avila, C., Biffin, T., Calatrava, J., Dartee, K., Douai, A., Gnonlonfin, A., Hérivaux, C., Marchal, R., Moncoulon, D., Piton, G., 2021. Is it worth investing in NBS aiming at reducing water risks? Insights from the economic assessment of three European case studies. *Nature-Based Solutions* 1, 100002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbsj.2021.100002>.
- Livesley, S.J., McPherson, E.G., Calfapietra, C., 2016. The Urban Forest and Ecosystem Services: Impacts on Urban Water, Heat, and Pollution Cycles at the Tree, Street, and City Scale. *J. Environ. Qual.* 45 (1), 119–124. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2015.11.0567>.
- Locatelli, L., Guerrero, M., Russo, B., Martínez-Gomariz, E., Sunyer, D., Martínez, M., 2020. Socio-Economic Assessment of Green Infrastructure for Climate Change Adaptation in the Context of Urban Drainage Planning. *Sustainability* 12 (9), 3792. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12093792>.
- Lopez Gunn, E., van der Keur, P., Le Coent, P., Giordano, R., 2023. *Water Security in a New World*. Springer.
- Martín-López, B., Gómez-Baggethun, E., Lomas, P., Montes, C., 2009. Effects of spatial and temporal scales on cultural services valuation. *Journal of Environmental Management* 90, 1050–1059. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2008.03.013>.
- Matos Silva, C., Serro, J., Dinis Ferreira, P., Teotónio, I., 2019. The socioeconomic feasibility of greening rail stations: A case study in Lisbon. *Eng. Econ.* 64 (2), 167–190. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0013791X.2018.1470272>.
- McPherson, E. G. (2003). A Benefit-Cost Analysis of Ten Street Tree Species in Modesto, California. *U.S. Arboriculture & Urban Forestry*, 29(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.48044/jauf.2003.001>.
- Melo, C., Teotónio, I., Silva, C.M., Cruz, C.O., 2020. What's the economic value of greening transport infrastructures? The case of the underground passages in Lisbon. *Sustain. Cities Soc.* 56, 102083. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2020.102083>.
- Molinos-Senante, M., Hernández-Sancho, F., Sala-Garrido, R., 2010. Economic feasibility study for wastewater treatment: A cost-benefit analysis. *Sci. Total Environ.* 408 (20), 4396–4402. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2010.07.014>.
- Moore, M.A., Boardman, A.E., Vining, A.R., 2013. More appropriate discounting: The rate of social time preference and the value of the social discount rate. *Journal of Benefit-Cost Analysis* 4 (1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jbca-2012-0008>.
- Nature4Cities. (2018). NBS multi-scalar and multi-thematic typology and associated database.
- Neumann, V.A., Hack, J., 2022. Revealing and assessing the costs and benefits of nature-based solutions within a real-world laboratory in Costa Rica. *Environ. Impact Assess. Rev.* 93, 106737. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2022.106737>.
- Niu, H., Clark, C., Zhou, J., Adriaens, P., 2010. Scaling of Economic Benefits from Green Roof Implementation in Washington, DC. *Environ. Sci. Tech.* 44, 4302–4308. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es902456x>.
- Nordman, E.E., Isely, E., Isely, P., Denning, R., 2018. Benefit-cost analysis of stormwater green infrastructure practices for Grand Rapids, Michigan, USA. *J. Clean. Prod.* 200, 501–510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.07.152>.
- Nurmi, V., Votsis, A., Perrels, A., Lehvāvirta, S., 2016. Green Roof Cost-Benefit Analysis: Special Emphasis on Scenic Benefits. *Journal of Benefit-Cost Analysis* 7 (3), 488–522. <https://doi.org/10.1017/bca.2016.18>.
- O'Mahony, T., 2021. Cost-Benefit Analysis and the environment: The time horizon is of the essence. *Environ. Impact Assess. Rev.* 89, 106587. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2021.106587>.
- Oecd, 2018. *Cost-Benefit Analysis and the Environment: Further Developments and Policy Use*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.
- Pascual, U., Palomo, I., Adams, W.M., Chan, K.M.A., Daw, T.M., Garmendia, E., Gómez-Baggethun, E., De Groot, R.S., Mace, G.M., Martín-López, B., Phelps, J., 2017. Off-stage ecosystem service burdens: A blind spot for global sustainability. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 12 (7), 075001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa7392>.
- Perini, K., Rosasco, P., 2016. Is greening the building envelope economically sustainable? An analysis to evaluate the advantages of economy of scope of vertical greening systems and green roofs. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 20, 328–337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2016.08.002>.
- Rau, A.-L., von Wehrden, H., Abson, D.J., 2018. Temporal Dynamics of Ecosystem Services. *Ecol. Econ.* 151, 122–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2018.05.009>.
- Raymond, C., Frantzeskaki, N., Kabisch, N., Berry, P., Breil, M., Nita, M., Geneletti, D., Calfapietra, C., 2017. A framework for assessing and implementing the co-benefits of nature-based solutions in urban areas. *Environ Sci Policy* 77, 15–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2017.07.008>.
- Rosasco, P., Perini, K., 2018. Evaluating the economic sustainability of a vertical greening system: A Cost-Benefit Analysis of a pilot project in mediterranean area. *Build. Environ.* 142, 524–533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2018.06.017>.
- Sandin, L., Olsson, J., Hanson, H., Sadat Nickayin, S., Wilke, M., Koivula, M., Rastas, M., Enge, C., Öie Kville, K., Lorentzi Wall, L., Hoffmann, C.C., Prastardóttir, R., Seifert-Dähnn, I., Furusetth, I.S., Baattrup-Pedersen, A., Zak, D., Alkan, 2022. Working with Nature-Based Solutions. Synthesis and mapping of status in the Nordics, Nordic Council of Ministers.
- Schoen, V., Caputo, S., Blythe, C., 2020. Valuing Physical and Social Output: A Rapid Assessment of a London Community Garden. *Sustainability* 12 (13), 5452. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12135452>.
- Shazmin, S.A.A., Zulkifli, N., 2020. Green roof for sustainable urban flash flood control via cost benefit approach for local authority. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 57, 126876. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2020.126876>.
- Shin, E., Kim, H., 2015. Analysing Green Roof Effects in an Urban Environment: A Case of Bangbae-dong, Seoul. *Journal of Asian Architecture and Building Engineering* 14 (2), 315–322. <https://doi.org/10.3130/jaabe.14.315>.
- Shin, E., Kim, H., 2019. Benefit-Cost Analysis of Green Roof Initiative Projects: The Case of Jung-gu, Seoul. *Sustainability* 11 (12), 3319. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11123319>.
- Soares, A.L., Rego, F.C., McPherson, E.G., Simpson, J.R., Peper, P.J., Xiao, Q., 2011. Benefits and costs of street trees in Lisbon, Portugal. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 10 (2), 69–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2010.12.001>.
- Swann, S., Blandford, L., Cheng, S., Cook, J., Miller, A., Barr, R., 2021. Public International Funding of Nature-based Solutions for Adaptation: A Landscape Assessment. World Resources Institute. <https://doi.org/10.46830/wriwp.20.00065>.
- Swarr, T.E., Hunkeler, D., Klöpffer, W., Pesonen, H.-L., Citroth, A., Brent, A.C., Pagan, R., 2011. Environmental life-cycle costing: A code of practice. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 16 (5), 389–391. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-011-0287-5>.
- Teotónio, I., Silva, C.M., Cruz, C.O., 2018. Eco-solutions for urban environments regeneration: The economic value of green roofs. *J. Clean. Prod.* 199, 121–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.07.084>.
- Teotónio, I., Silva, C.M., Cruz, C.O., 2021. Economics of green roofs and green walls: A literature review. *Sustain. Cities Soc.* 69, 102781. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2021.102781>.
- Velasco, M., Russo, B., Cabello, À., Termes, M., Sunyer, D., Malgrat, P., 2018. Assessment of the effectiveness of structural and nonstructural measures to cope with global change impacts in Barcelona: Assessment of the effectiveness of structural and nonstructural measures. *J. Flood Risk Manage.* 11, S55–S68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfr3.12247>.
- G.-J. Wilbers Investing in Urban Blue-Green Infrastructure—Assessing the Costs and Benefits of Stormwater Management in a Peri-Urban Catchment in Oslo 2022 Norway.
- Wild, T.C., Henneberry, J., Gill, L., 2017. Comprehending the multiple 'values' of green infrastructure – Valuing nature-based solutions for urban water management from multiple perspectives. *Environ. Res.* 158, 179–187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.05.043>.
- World Bank, 2021. A Catalogue of Nature-Based Solutions for Urban Resilience. World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/36507>.
- Wu, T., Smith, R.E., 2011. Economic benefits for green roofs: A case study of the skaggs pharmacy building, university of utah. *International Journal of Design & Nature and Ecodynamics* 6 (2), 122–138. <https://doi.org/10.2495/DNE-V6-N2-122-138>.

- Yao, L., Chini, A., Zeng, R., 2018. Integrating cost-benefits analysis and life cycle assessment of green roofs: A case study in Florida. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment* 26, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10807039.2018.1514251>.
- Zhuang, J., Liang, Z., Lin, T., & De Guzman, F. (2007). Theory and Practice in the Choice of Social Discount Rate for Cost-Benefit Analysis: A Survey. ERD Working Paper Series, No. 94, Asian Development Bank (ADB), Manila.
- Zinzi, M., Agnoli, S., 2012. Cool and green roofs. An energy and comfort comparison between passive cooling and mitigation urban heat island techniques for residential buildings in the Mediterranean region. *Energ. Buildings* 55, 66–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2011.09.024>.